

Future Circular Collider

TECHNICAL NOTE

FEASIBILITY STUDY OF A TRANS-JURA FCC SCENARIO WITH ONE TRANSFER LINE FROM THE LHC

Document identifier:	FCC-2012011930-ATU EDMS 2480767 10.5281/zenodo.4545604
Date:	01/12/2020
Work package/unit:	WP3.1
Organisation:	CERN
Document prepared by:	Alexandra Tudora (CERN), John Osborne (CERN), Volker Mertens (CERN)
Version:	V 1.0
Status:	RELEASED
Domain:	Engineering
Keywords:	Civil engineering, FCC, feasibility, geology, Bresse Graben, Bresse Marls, Jura, limestone, karst, alternative locations

Abstract:

Several placements have been investigated during the feasibility studies for the Future Circular Collider (FCC), which is envisaged to be the successor of the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) at CERN. The conceptual design of FCC considers a 97.75 km long, quasi-circular tunnel, situated in the Geneva Basin and with tunnel connections to the LHC or a superconducting SPS for the beam transfer lines. The study described in this technical note considers an alternative scenario for the placement of the FCC, on the west side of the Jura mountains, in the so called “Bresse Graben” formation. Beam would be transported through a single ~60 km long transfer line from the LHC. This note summarises the findings of a civil engineering feasibility study for such a ‘trans-Jura’ scenario.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION..... 3

2. OBJECTIVE 3

3. PLACEMENT AND TOPOGRAPGY 3

4. GEOLOGY OF THE REGION 5

 4.1. BRESSE MARLS 5

 4.2. JURA LIMESTONE..... 9

5. CIVIL ENGINEERING FINDINGS 10

 5.1. TUNNELLING IN THE BRESSE FORMATION..... 10

 5.2. TUNNELLING THROUGH THE JURA LIMESTONE..... 11

 5.3. COST AND SCHEDULE CONSIDERATIONS 12

 5.4. ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS 13

 5.4.1. Protected zones..... 13

 5.4.2. Excavation material..... 14

6. CONCLUSIONS 14

7. REFERENCES..... 15

ANNEXES 16

 A.1. BOREHOLES LOCATIONS AND LOGS..... 16

 A.2. SUMMARY OF CIVIL ENGINEERING COST ESTIMATES 24

1. INTRODUCTION

Several locations have been investigated for the feasibility study of the Future Circular Collider (FCC), which is envisaged to be the successor of the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) at CERN. The conceptual design of FCC considers a 97.75 km long, quasi-circular tunnel, situated in the Geneva Basin and with tunnel connections to the LHC or a superconducting SPS for the transfer lines. The tunnel is buried deep underground at an average elevation of 300 mASL. The alignment of the tunnel has been optimised based on criteria such as geology along the tunnel, overburden, shafts depth, surface locations and connection to existing LHC accelerator facilities at CERN [1].

An alternative location, considered in the FCC feasibility studies, is on the west side of the Jura, in so-called “Bresse” formation. The findings of a civil engineering feasibility study at this location are summarised in this technical note. Two previous studies at CERN investigated the feasibility of a future collider in surrounding regions, namely one in 1997 evaluating the feasibility of a 36 km and 113 km tunnel so called “Projet Dombes” [2] and another in 2001 which investigated the feasibility of a “Very Large Hadron Collider (VLHC)” of 113 km and 240 km circumference. These locations were found to be unfavourable due to challenging geology and difficult connections to the LHC [3].

2. OBJECTIVE

The objective of this study is to give an overview of the civil engineering risk factors, cost and schedule implications if the 100 km long tunnel proposed for FCC is situated to the west of the Jura, with a single transfer line connection from the LHC.

The study focuses on the topography and the geology in the proposed location of the FCC ring and the transfer line tunnel, to determine the main civil engineering challenges and potential impact on cost and construction schedule. Some remarks regarding environmental factors (protected areas, excavation material and impact on the existing infrastructure) are acknowledged in chapter 5.4.

3. PLACEMENT AND TOPOGRAPGY

The alternative location proposed for this study and the transfer line connection to the LHC is shown in Fig. 1. The FCC tunnel footprint is delimited by the Jura mountains to the east, the Saône river in the west, the city of Mâcon in the South-West, Bourg-en Bresse in the South-East and the commune of Romenay to the north. Except for these three main urban settlements, the areas within the FCC footprint are less urbanised than the CDR baseline scenario. Lyon is situated approximately 50 km further south of the footprint.

To connect to the existing accelerator at CERN, a transfer line tunnel of approximately 60 km is required, which must cross through the Jura mountains.

Figure 1: Placement of FCC tunnel shown in light blue (the shape of the FCC is simply represented here by a circle). The LHC is shown in dark blue and the proposed transfer line connection in red. Main urban settlements are highlighted in green.

The terrain in the Bresse region is relatively flat with an average altitude of 230 m. In contrast, the surrounding topographical features such as the Jura reach altitudes of over 1600 m (Fig. 2). The software suite ArcGIS was used to plot the layout of the FCC in the studied location, as shown in Fig. 3. The elevation of the tunnel is assumed to be 150 mASL, considering a minimum ground cover of 30 m to avoid radiation concerns. Along its circumference, the depth of the tunnel under the surface varies between 30 m and 110 m.

Figure 2: Simplified scheme of the topographical profile showing the Jura mountains and valleys, the Bresse region and the Mâconnais which is part of the eastern side of the Massif Central

Figure 3: Capture from ArcGIS showing the topography above the tunnel location in amber. The position of the tunnel is represented by the blue line at a constant elevation of 150 mASL.

4. GEOLOGY OF THE REGION

4.1. BRESSE MARLS

The geology of the region is characterised by the formation called “Bresse Graben” which is part of the European Cenozoic Rift System that began to form during the Middle Eocene [4]. The “Bresse Graben” extends for 200 km and is delimited by the Burgundy Sill to the north, the Valence Basin to the south, the Jura to the east and the Massif Central to the west [7]. The stratigraphy of the Bresse Graben is depicted in Fig. 5 [5]. The tertiary formations (Pliocene) have a thickness of approximately 300 m (Fig. 6) and are comprised of “a sedimentary complex largely made up of fluvial Chaux Pebles in the north, and of lacustrine, lignite-bearing Bresse Marls and conglomeratic Bresse sediments in the south, directly north of Lyon” [5]. During the subsidence of the Bresse Graben in the Late Pliocene after the Jura thrusting had ceased, a large swampy area with fluvial deposition of coarse-grained sediments was established in a broad sagging basin “connected to the area occupying the concurrently submerged paleo-Rhone valley. The Bresse Graben is presently uplifted and subject to erosion.” [5]. The eastern margins are characterised by thrust faults of the Jura Mountains [4].

The lithology is heterogeneous within the Bresse Graben basin. This is defined by layers of glacial deposits characteristic to “Bresse Meridionale” in the south part called “Dombes” [6] where the scenario of a VLHC was studied in 1997. In contrast, the proposed location in this study places the FCC tunnel in the Louhans basin (Fig. 4), where the layers intersected by the tunnel is characterised by the Bresse Marls.

Figure 4: Map showing the Bresse Graben basin.

Figure 5: Lithostratigraphy of the Bresse Graben [5].

Figure 6: Sedimentary fill of the Bresse Graben [5].

Borehole logs available from BRGM were reviewed along the circumference of the tunnel to get a better understanding of the lithology of the ground which the tunnel would intersect. The depth of some of these boreholes goes as deep as 2521 m (Annex 1). Fig. 7 shows the location of 8 selected boreholes, denoted by “B01” to “B08”, along the tunnel circumference.

Given the depth of the tunnel, the principal formations crossed are Bresse Marls and Bresse Alluviums. The borehole logs show the variable lithology along the tunnel, with dominant Bresse marls formations characterised by a complex sedimentary mix of sandy clays, marly sandstone, limestone marls, sandy marls and localised lignite (e.g. for B03, B05, B06, B07, B08). Approaching the Saône river, the lithology of the boreholes highlights a top layer of alluvium formations made up by gravels and lacustrine deposits made up by marls and sand (e.g. B04). Some boreholes show localised presence of gypsum (e.g. B03, B08).

Figure 7: Location of selected boreholes along the proposed location for FCC in the Bresse formation (geological basemap: BRGM Infoterre).

4.2. JURA LIMESTONE

To ensure the connection with the LHC, which will be used as a booster accelerator for the FCC (NB: beam could also come from a superconducting SPS, geographically close to the LHC), a transfer line is required which must cross through the Jura mountains. Limestones of Jurassic to Cretaceous age are found in the Jura mountains with numerous fractures crossing the formations. Karst networks are expected to be present within the limestone. The Jura mountains rise in altitudes over 1600 mASL, leading to high overburden on the transfer line tunnel, up to 1300 m. This is depicted in Fig. 8.

Figure 8: Profile of the transfer line tunnel connecting FCC and LHC and assumed intermediate shaft locations T1 to T4. The maximum distance between two consecutive shafts is ~13.5 km (between T1 and T2).

5. CIVIL ENGINEERING FINDINGS

5.1. TUNNELLING IN THE BRESSE FORMATION

One of the key parameters when choosing the tunnelling technique and ground improvement measures is the stability of the ground during excavation. Tunnelling in soft ground such as clay, silt, sand and gravel requires particular techniques compared to excavating in rock, in order to manage the shifting nature of the soil. Immediate support is generally required when excavating in soft ground.

The presence of clay is shown in the lithological description of the BRGM borehole logs and various reports. Depending on its composition, swelling is one of the problems that can occur in clay. Without further investigations, the swelling potential of the Bresse clay is unknown. Nonetheless, evidence so far shows that swelling and shrinkage is typical for the clays and marls in the French area of Saône-et-Loire, with Bresse formations being more prone to this behaviour in comparison with the clays and marls in other French areas. Furthermore, reports show high content of montmorillonite which is a clay mineral susceptible to volume change. Squeezing and sealing of the ground can create high pressures on tunnels supports and may cause movements in the long term [7]. An example of tunnel deformations due to swelling behaviour of the ground is shown in Fig. 9 [8].

Some of the boreholes mention “gypse” or gypsum. Gypsum is a hydrophilic material, which can also lead to the risk of swelling. This might be an issue for the cavern structures as the large, non-circular spans are more prone to point loading. It may also cause movements in the beam line in the long term.

Figure 9: Example of tunnel invert heave due to swelling ground behaviour in the Chienberg road tunnel.

The geotechnical parameters and hydrogeology in “Bresse marls” and clays must be studied in order to determine the most suitable design and construction methods for the underground structures in these formations. Considering the available information, additional support measures are envisaged for the construction of the caverns and shafts. Shielded TBMs should be used for the main tunnel boring. Similar recommendations were made by GADZ for the VLHC study in 2001 [3].

Earth Pressure Balance (EPB) machines are generally employed in fine-grained cohesive soils. EPBs use the excavated material to support the tunnel face during excavation and are able to control ground movements and minimise settlements caused by tunnelling activities. Examples where EPB machines were recently used is the Grand Paris Express where 90 % of the excavation was done in similar heterogeneous soft ground made up of marl, limestone, clay, chalk, alluvions, gravel, marl, gypsum, sand marl, and scree [9].

The main advantages for placing the FCC in the “bressian” basin are the reduced shafts depths and the lower overburden on the main tunnel. On the other hand, aquifers and elevated groundwater levels are expected in this region. For example, water levels were recorded at 7-8 m depth near Bourg-en-Bresse [10]. Similar to the conceptual design of shafts in the moraines of the Lemman basin, diaphragm walls or similar temporary support would be required for the construction of the shafts in bresse formations. The construction of large caverns in unstable and saturated soils would raise significant difficulties.

5.2. TUNNELLING THROUGH THE JURA LIMESTONE

The transfer line to the FCC would have to be approximately 60 km long, in order that the FCC main tunnel avoids the Jura limestone. The transfer line tunnel requires a smaller diameter than the main tunnel and goes mainly through Jura limestone. This is challenging for excavation due to karstic features formed by chemical weathering of the rock. It is common for karsts to be filled with water and sediment. This can lead to water inflows and instability of the excavation. CERN has experienced significant issues when excavating in limestone, in contrast to tunnelling in molasse. During the construction of LEP, sector 3 to 4 was excavated in the Jura limestone. Water inflows of 100 l/s were recorded during tunnelling. Higher water pressures, up to 30 bars, could be encountered when tunnelling under the Jura [11].

Temporary and permanent drawdown of the water table can lead to aquifer depletion. This can also be associated with surface settlement, particularly if sand and silts are transported by the inflow. In areas where karstic features are deemed too large, ground treatment may not be possible. Groundwater inflows could also vary in time and depend on seasonal changes, more pronounced during heavy rainfall. This would need constant monitoring. It has been the case in the LHC sector 3-4 where maintenance works were more extensive than in the other LHC sectors seated in the molasse basin. The civil engineers who conducted tunnel inspections found the LHC sector 3-4 to be in poor condition. Extensive sediment ingress has been recorded. Pressure gauges measured hydrostatic pressures over 12 bar. A steel mesh has been installed in sections of the crown to prevent spalling concrete from falling onto sensitive equipment (Fig. 10) [12].

Figure 10: Tunnel condition in the LHC Sector 3-4. Left: extensive sediment ingress near a waterproofed construction joint and drip protection in the roof. Right: steel mesh installed in the crown with a water pressure relief valve drilled through the lining.

Problematic for the Jura tunnel are the triassic marls underlying the limestone, containing the mineral anhydrite. The creation of space underground and the introduction of water from the tunnel excavation may cause the anhydrite to become saturated, swell and lead to deformations of the tunnel [13].

Deep shafts would be required for ventilation and access. Those requirements have not been studied at this stage. Assuming a maximum distance between shafts of 13.5 km, 4 shafts are proposed along the 60 km long injection tunnel. Their depth could reach up to 530 m. Deeper shafts were constructed for the Gotthard tunnel, notably the Sedrun shaft which is about 800 m deep. This was a challenging task not only for the civil engineers but also for the geodetic engineers, as tolerances for the shaft and tunnel alignment are more difficult to achieve with increasing shaft depth [14].

The main issues arise when karstic features and faults are encountered, leading to groundwater inflows. When tunnelling through faulted and karstic ground, extensive monitoring and pilot hole drilling would be required to identify and treat these zones before advancing the boring. The drill-and-blast technique was used for LEP tunnels under the Jura. Although modern TBM technology can be used for tunnel boring in limestone under high pressures, drill-and-blast is usually preferred as it allows access to the excavation face, especially where karstic features could be encountered. Conventional tunnelling methods are likely to be more economical than mechanised methods in these difficult ground conditions [15].

5.3. COST AND SCHEDULE CONSIDERATIONS

A cost estimate of the FCC tunnels, caverns and shafts was provided for the conceptual design baseline. These estimates were determined based on reasonable knowledge of important ground parameters of the molasse, which enabled the selection of the ground excavation technology, type and thickness of lining, additional ground treatments and rock support measures. Similarly, the construction schedule was developed based on the performance of selected TBMs and advancement rates achieved previously on similar projects, such as LEP and LHC.

All this information is necessary to determine a more accurate cost estimate for the trans-Jura scenario. Its geotechnical parameters have so far not been studied. Nevertheless, a cost estimate for the trans-Jura scenario was prepared using the bottom-up approach, using similar unit rates as provided by ILF in the Cost and Schedule Study for FCC [16]. The unit rates for excavating in soft ground and limestone have been applied. The expected accuracy range of the estimate is up to 50 %, as this study could be classified as a Class 4 in the Process Industries Matrix [17].

The depth of the shaft varies between 40 and 85 m around the FCC ring. Fig. 11 shows the assumed locations of the shafts, considering a similar distance between points as in the CDR baseline. Unit rates for soft ground have been assumed for all shafts along their entire depth, at the 12 access points. The estimated price for shaft excavation in soft ground is 1,420 EUR/m³. This is higher than in the CDR where the average estimated price for shaft excavation in the molasse is 1,250 EUR/m³. To recall that in the baseline location most parts of the shafts are excavated in molasse, except for the top 10-35 m of soft ground at each shaft. However, because the shafts in the trans-Jura scenario are less deep as compared to the shafts in the CDR baseline, the total cost of the shafts at the 12 points is reduced by half. This is outweighed in the trans-Jura scenario by the deep shafts required along the beam transfer tunnel (Fig. 8).

Figure 11: Profile of FCC tunnel and topography showing assumed shafts locations.

In the baseline design, the two transfer tunnels are 4 m in diameter and together 11.8 km long. The additional 48.2 km in the trans-Jura scenario add 1,152 MEUR for the tunnels and 300 MEUR for the four shafts.

The additional tunnelling for the transfer line does not only increase the civil engineering costs but could also delay the construction schedule. Mined excavations such as drill-and-blast would be preferred for better accessibility to the face of the excavation and because of the versatility of this technique to cope with variable ground and groundwater conditions. However, drill-and-blast achieves lower advance rates than TBMs. For example, the average rate achieved for LEP TBM tunnels was 30 m/day, while it was 3 m/day with drill-and-blast in the Jura limestone [13]. The EPB machines tunnelling for the Grand Paris Express achieved a record of 35 m/day advance rates [18].

The cost of the FCC main tunnel is assumed to be 36 % higher in the trans-Jura scenario than in the CDR baseline scenario because pressurised TBMs (such as EPBs or Slurry TBMs) are required in order to maintain the face pressure in the soft ground. Tunnel lining and waterproofing requirements are also more onerous. The choice of TBMs has also an impact on the construction schedule. Double-shield TBMs were chosen in the conceptual design studies for FCC main tunnel because they can achieve higher speeds as compared to other types of TBMs. This is due to the fact that double-shield TBMs can operate in two modes and the pre-cast concrete segments can be erected while the machine is boring [19].

As mentioned before, the maintenance works in LHC sector 3-4 were considerably more important than in other sectors. Similarly, higher maintenance costs should be expected for the 60 km injection tunnel. The total whole-life cost is important when comparing different options for tunnelling projects.

A summary of the cost estimate is shown in Appendix 2. The total estimated cost of the civil engineering for the FCC trans-Jura scenario is 7,304 MEUR. This is 36 % higher than the cost estimate for the CDR scenario, for which the total cost was estimated to 5,374 MEUR.

5.4. ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS

5.4.1. Protected zones

Civil engineering activities can have an impact on the natural environment through air pollution, noise and waste and bear the risk of aquifer pollution. An investigation of the subsurface of the Bresse region was carried

out in 1974, which shows evidence of a carboniferous basin, salt deposits and natural water reservoirs [6]. Important aquifers are surrounding the south and west borders of the tunnel, mainly linked to the presence of the Saône and Rhône rivers [2]. BRGM Infoterre shows Protected Zones such as natural parks in Jura mountains (Fig. 12) [20].

Figure 12: Protected Zones shown in the Jura and Bresse region. The areas in green refer to Natural Zones of ecological interest [20].

Furthermore, a shallower tunnel (30 m deep in some areas) would introduce the risk of disturbing adjacent infrastructure. When new tunnels are being built at a shallow depth, constant monitoring of ground movements and potential settlements are essential in order to assess the impact on existing infrastructure. Ground treatments such as compensation grouting might be required to reduce the risk of induced settlements. The location of the shafts and any planning or approvals issues have not been studied; to avoid urban or protected areas.

5.4.2. Excavation material

Based on the conceptual design studies, approximately 9 million of cubic meters of spoil will result from the excavations for FCC tunnels, caverns and shafts. The selected location in the conceptual design places the FCC in the Molasse basin and therefore about 90 % of the excavation material will be molasse. Although the molasse has proved to be a good rock for tunneling, its re-use potential is not evident.

The excavation material from tunneling in the Bresse marls and Jura limestone might have more obvious applications and potential for the re-use. However, the quantity of spoil is significantly increased by the additional ≈ 50 km of tunneling for the transfer lines (in this case limestone).

6. CONCLUSIONS

Construction of the LEP and LHC tunnels suggests the molasse is an excellent tunnelling medium and there is a better understanding of construction risks than in the Bresse formations. The molasse is known to be relatively impermeable with evidence of reduced hydrostatic pressures. In comparison, increased waterproofing would be necessary in Bresse marls and Jura limestone. Ground squeezing and swelling potential due to presence of clay in Bresse marls can create high pressures on tunnel support and construction of large span caverns is expected to be problematic in unstable ground. Although the Bresse region is relatively flat and the depth of the FCC shafts can be significantly reduced, the additional 60 km tunnel and deeper shafts for the transfer lines to ensure connection with the LHC makes the trans-Jura scenario less attractive. This is mainly due to higher construction risks and increase in civil engineering costs by approximately 36 % as compared to the CDR baseline scenario.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] M. Benedikt, J. Gutleber, F. Zimmermann, *Future Circular Collider Study. Volume 3: The Hadron Collider (FCC-hh) Conceptual Design Report. CERN accelerator report*, CERN-ACC-2018-0058, Geneva, 2018, <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1140/epjst/e2019-900087-0>.
- [2] J. F. Hotellier, Géotechnique Appliquée – Deriaz SA (GADZ), *Projets Futurs. Eléments géologique pour l'étude de faisabilité*, Genève, Décembre 1997, EDMS no:1221041, <https://edms.cern.ch/document/1221041/1>.
- [3] J. C. Fourneaux, Géotechnique Appliquée – Deriaz SA (GADZ), *Projets VLHC. Eléments géologique pour l'étude de faisabilité*, Genève, Juin 2001, EDMS no:1221041, <https://edms.cern.ch/document/1221041/1>.
- [4] V. Gennes, 2013, *The Rhinegraben – Bresse Graben System, European Crust and Topo Europe*, http://www.ged.rwth-aachen.de/files/documents/document_1909.pdf.
- [5] W. Sissingh, *Comparative Tertiary stratigraphy of the Rhine Graben, Bresse Graben and Molasse Basin: correlation of Alpine foreland events*, Netherlands, 1997, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-1951\(98\)00243-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-1951(98)00243-1).
- [6] M. J. Lienhardt, *Synthese geologique de la Bresse (01). Eléments pour une planification de l'utilisation du sous-sol*, BRGM, Septembre 1974, <https://infoterre.brgm.fr/rapports/74-SGN-308-JAL.pdf>.
- [7] C. Butscher, P. Huggenberger, E. Zechner, H. Einstein, *Relation between hydrogeological setting and swelling potential of clay-sulfate rocks in tunnelling*, July 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enggeo.2011.05.009>
- [8] B. Schädlich, *A tunnelling case study in swelling rock*, November 2012, https://online.tugraz.at/tug_online/voe_main2.getVollText?pDocumentNr=286462&pCurrPk=69021
- [9] T. Thomas, *Tunnelling Journal, First Grand Paris Express TBM assembly*, February 2018, <https://tunnellingjournal.com/first-grand-paris-express-tbm-assembly/>
- [10] D. Jaufret, BRGM, *Ville de Bourg-en-Bresse (Ain)*. Available at : <http://infoterre.brgm.fr/rapports/RR-34024-FR.pdf>
- [11] H. Schopper, *LEP – The Lord of the Colliders Rings at CERN*. Geneva, 2009. Springer.
- [12] LS2 Tunnel Inspection Report, WP3: LHC Sector 3-4. EDMS nr: 2280896. <https://edms.cern.ch/document/2280896/2>
- [13] J. Osborne, C. Waaijer, ARUP, GADZ, *Prefeasibility study for an 80km tunnel project at CERN*, CERN, Geneva, July 2012. EDMS nr: 1233485. <https://edms.cern.ch/document/1233485/1>
- [14] IGS, *The surveyors in the longest tunnel in the world*. February 2013. https://issuu.com/sigwerbgmbh/docs/sonderdruck_gotthard_english
- [15] AMBERG, *FCC Risk assessment*, CERN, November 2015. EDMS no: 1561971 <https://edms.cern.ch/document/1561971/1>
- [16] ILF Cost and Schedule Study. EDMS no: 2050504. <https://edms.cern.ch/document/2050504/1>
- [17] SMB-SE-FAS Quality manual. EDMS no: 2019816. <https://edms.cern.ch/document/2019816/1>
- [18] SWS, *Grand Paris Express Line 14 lot 4 tunnel excavation completed*. <http://www.swsglobal.com/2020/09/23/grand-paris-express-line-14-lot-4-tunnel-excavation-completed/>
- [19] Herrenknecht, *Double Shield TBM*, <https://www.herrenknecht.com/en/products/productdetail/double-shield-tbm/>
- [20] BRGM cartes géologiques, <https://infoterre.brgm.fr/page/cartes-geologiques>.

ANNEXES

A.1. BOREHOLES LOCATIONS AND LOGS

B01 location

B01 Log

BSS001PZXX

06264X0003/PSX1

Log validé

Profondeur
De 0,0 à 600 m Rafraîchir

Profondeur	Formation	Lithologie	Lithologie	Stratigraphie	Altitude
29.00	Calcaires graveleux et oolithiques très blanc à Algues, Bryozoaires		Calcaire jaune ocre, micrograveleux à grumeleux; intercalations d'argile jaune ocre, plastique	Bathonien	442.10
40.00			Alémenance de marne et de calcaire micrograveleux gris bleu		431.10
54.00			Calcaire jaune ocre, finement oolithique		417.10
			Perte totale: formation équivalente calcaire graveleux et oolithique (701 - 840m)	Aalénien à Bathonien	
240.00	Calcaires gréseux roux à Bélemnites "Banc de Roc", Gryphaea gigantea		Argile	Pliensbachien	231.10
268.00			Banc de Roc: calcaire gréseux		203.10
272.00			Argile		199.10
329.00	Calcaire marneux gris ou brun, noduleux, glauconieux à Bélemnites		Calcaire cryptocristallin gris clair, localement glauconieux; intercalations de marne noire glauconieuse	Hettangien à Sinémurien inférieur	142.10
360.00			Calcaire microcristallin, gris brun, glauconieux; organogènes et calcaire argileux		111.10
374.00			Calcaire gréseux et grès calcaire	Rhétien	97.10
380.00			Grès fin, blanc, carbonaté, compact, argile noire, dolomie cryptocristalline	91.10	
401.00	Argiles bariolées dolomitiques du Keuper supérieur		Argile bariolée; intercalations de dolomie cryptocristalline	Keuper supérieur	70.10
420.50			Anhydrite massive; intercalation de dolomie cryptocristalline		50.60
438.00			Argile bariolée; intercalations d'anhydrite et de gypse		33.10
479.00	Argilites à gypse et anhydrite du Keuper		Silt et argile sableuse gris verdâtre	Keuper inférieur	-7.90
524.00			Sel massif; intercalations argileuses; inclusions d'anhydrite		-52.90
580.00	Argiles bariolées dolomitiques du Keuper supérieur		Argile bariolée; intercalations d'anhydrite	Keuper supérieur	-108.90

B02 location

B02 log

BSS001PCHW

06035X1004/PETROL

Log géologique numérisé

Nombre de passes : 27 - [Afficher le log validé](#)

Nombre de niveaux : 7

Profondeur	Lithologie	Stratigraphie
De 0 à 6 m	ARGILE SABLEUSE	QUATERNAIRE
De 6 à 184 m	ARGILE SABLEUSE, LIGNITE	NEOGENE
De 184 à 265 m	ALTERNANCE SABLE GROSSIER, MARNE CALCAIRE	NEOGENE
De 265 à 272 m	SABLE GROSSIER ARGILEUX	NEOGENE
De 272 à 594 m	MARNE PLUS OU MOINS INDUREE	OLIGOCENE
De 594 à 663 m	SABLE A PASSEES GRESEUSES, CALCAIRE POREUX	OLIGOCENE
De 663 à 665.2 m	CALCAIRE BLANC CRAYEUX	CRETACE-SUP

B03 location

B03 log

BSS001PZWK

06262X0001/BR101

Log validé

Profondeur
De 0.0 à 600 m Rafraichir

Profondeur	Formation	Lithologie	Lithologie	Stratigraphie	Altitude
13.00	Marnes de Bresse et formations plio-quaternaires bressanes indifférenciées à faciès argilo-marneux dominants		Argile sableuse jaune et sable argileux jaune.	Pliocène à Quaternaire	192.00
40.00			Marne argileuse finement sableuse gris vert ou gris, micacée. Lignite associé à une argile brunâtre à 40m et de 52 à 62m. Nombreux débris végétaux. Débris de petits mollusques.		165.00
41.00				Pliocène	164.00
52.00					153.00
62.00					143.00
115.00			Marne argileuse grise et jaune, avec nodules de gypse saccharoïde ou de calcaire jaune ferrugineux. Fossiles : limnées, hélix.	Néogène	90.00
305.00	Molasses sableuses à Foraminifères et à lentilles conglomératiques		Sable molassique gris micacé comprenant des niveaux à gros galets calcaires ou siliceux blancs, crèmes, jaunes et rouges. Petits gastéropodes, débris végétaux. Conglomérat à éléments calcaires bruns, bréges, blancs ou jaunes.	Miocène	-100.00
340.00					-135.00
350.00	Faciès aquitaniens marneux et calcaires lacustres		Marne ou marne-calcaire gris clair, gris beige ou blanchâtre, avec niveaux de calcaire gris zoopliens et nodules ou lentilles de sable brun. A 391m, niveau de marne brune un peu bitumineuse. Nombreux débris de gastéropodes, ostracodes.	Aquitanien	-145.00
391.00					-186.00
392.00					-187.00
437.00			Marne rubanée grise, gris vert ou jaune, avec lentilles de sable noir et intercalations de marne tachetée.		-232.00
446.00					-241.00
522.00	Série continentale lacustre et salifère du fossé bressan		Marne grise à gris vert, comprenant de gros nodules irréguliers de gypse gris et blanc.	Stampien	
			Sel massif gris contenant des niveaux de marne grise avec des nodules ou bis d'anhydrite, et des nodules de gypse.		-317.00

B04 location

B04 log

BSS001PYNG

06253X0014/F

Log validé

Profondeur
De 0.0 à 135.0 m Rafraichir

Profondeur	Formation	Lithologie	Lithologie	Stratigraphie	Altitude
3.30	Alluvions anciennes Fv-w		Graviers	Pléistocène inférieur à Pléistocène moyen	173.70
4.85			Marne tourbeuse		172.15
9.10			Marne et sable		167.90
10.45			Marne		166.55
10.55			Graviers		166.45
13.15			Sable gris		163.85
17.05	Marnes et sables blancs lacustres de Bresse et Dombes (p1)		Marne tourbeuse	Pliocène inférieur	159.95
25.30			Marne grise		151.70
29.10			Sable gris		147.90
29.65			Lignite ou tourbe		147.35
30.25			Marne sableuse		146.75
45.63			Sable fin		131.37
61.00			Marne grise		116.00
81.08			Marne bariolée		95.92
81.68			Sable		95.32
82.50			Marne jaune		94.50
83.00		Sable	94.00		
105.00			Marne		72.00
135.00			Argile et marne bariolées (dominance rouge et blanc)		42.00

B05 location

B05 log

BSS001PYNC

06253X0010/S

Log validé

Profondeur
De 0.0 à 600 m Rafraîchir

Profondeur	Formation	Lithologie	Lithologie	Stratigraphie	Altitude
8.30	Marnes de Bresse et formations plio-quaternaires bressanes indifférenciées à faciès argilo-marneux dominants		Argile finement sableuse grise plastique.	Quaternaire	172.80
28.30			Graviers et galets siliceux gris.	Pléistocène	152.80
43.30			Argile finement sableuse grise.	Pliocène	137.80
152.30			Sable argileux avec niveaux de marnes gris verdâtre et passées plus ou moins importantes de lignite. Depuis 118m, sable plus grossier.	Miocène	28.80
160.30	20.80				
160.80	20.30				
162.30	Faciès aquitaniens marneux et calcaires lacustres		Argile gris verdâtre plastique avec fines passées de calcaire argileux blanchâtre légèrement crayeux.	Aquitanien	18.80
164.30			16.80		
169.30			11.80		
170.30			10.80		
179.30	Série continentale lacustre et salifère du fossé bressan		Marnes calcaires	Oligocène	1.80
181.30					-0.20
193.30					-12.20
194.30					-13.20
206.30					-25.20
297.30					-116.20
303.30					-122.20
305.80					-124.70
323.30	Conglomérat polygénique consolidé à ciment argilo-sableux ocre et éléments de calcaire jurassique (3/15cm), siliceux. Éléments calcaires : calcaire oolithique blanc à fond microcristallin, calcaire graveleux à fond micro ou cryptocristallin, calcaire cryptoc	Eocène	-142.20		
324.80			-143.70		
329.30			-148.20		
341.80			-160.70		
342.80			-161.70		
501.80			-320.70		
502.80			-321.70		
578.30			-397.20		

B06 location

B06 log

BSS001PZUY

06258X003/BR2

Log géologique numérisé

Nombre de passes : 28 - [Afficher le log validé](#)

Nombre de niveaux : 10

Profondeur	Lithologie	Stratigraphie
De 0 à 5 m	ARGILE SABLEUSE	QUATERNAIRE
De 5 à 285.63 m	MARNES A NIVEAUX SABLEUX	PLIOCENE
De 285.63 à 295.63 m	SABLES FINS ARGILEUX MOLASSIQUES	MIOCENE
De 295.63 à 825 m	MARNES, CALCAIRES, MARNES A GYPSE ET ANHYDRITE	OLIGOCENE
De 825 à 920 m	BRECHE CALCAIRE ET CALCAIRE	CRETACE-INF
De 920 à 1063 m	DOLOMIE, CALCAIRE ET MARNO-CALCAIRES	MALM
De 1063 à 1257 m	CALCAIRES: OOLITHIQUES, A CHAILLES ETC...	DOGGER
De 1257 à 1321 m	MARNES	LIAS
De 1321 à 1410 m	ARGILES, DOLOMIES, ANHYDRITE ET GRES	TRIAS
De 1410 à 1554 m	ARGILES ROUGES, GRES, CONGLOMERATS	PERMIEN

B07 location

B07 log

BSS001REVX

06512X0011/S

Log validé

Profondeur
 De 0.0 à 600 m [Rafraichir](#)

Profondeur	Formation	Lithologie	Lithologie	Stratigraphie	Altitude
44.00	Marnes de Bresse et formations plio-quaternaires bressanes indifférenciées à faciès argilo-marneux dominants			Pliocène à Quaternaire	184.00
50.00					178.00
80.00					148.00
85.00					143.00
102.00					126.00
110.00					118.00
112.00					116.00
120.00					108.00
157.00					71.00
168.00					60.00
230.00	Série continentale lacustre et salifère du fossé bressan			Miocène	-2.00
240.00					-12.00
268.00					-40.00
292.00					-64.00
351.00					-123.00
380.00	Oligocène			-152.00	
415.00				-187.00	
451.00				-223.00	
460.00	Série salifère du bassin de Valence			Oligocène inférieur	-232.00
471.00					-243.00
530.00	Série salifère du bassin de Valence			Oligocène inférieur	-302.00
550.00					-322.00
562.00					-334.00

B08 location

B08 log

BSS001QABG

06267X0022/EZ-02

Log validé

Profondeur
De 0.0 à 600 m Rafraichir

Profondeur	Formation	Lithologie	Lithologie	Stratigraphie	Altitude
125.20	Marnes de Bresse et formations plio-quaternaires bressanes indifférenciées à faciès argilo-marneux dominants		Plio-Quaternaire. Argile à marne sableuse, sable et grès calcaire, passées calcaires et niveaux ligniteux vers le bas.	Pliocène à Quaternaire	98.30
	Argiles à lignite et débris végétaux		Pontien. Marne à argile calcaire, niveaux ligniteux, de calcaire argileux, présence locale de gypse.	Messinien	
338.50	Molasses sableuses à Foraminifères et à lentilles conglomératiques		Tortonien. Sable molassique.	Miocène	-115.00
421.50	Faciès aquitaniens marneux et calcaires lacustres		Aquitanien. Calcaire argileux, marne et bancs calcaires. Présence de silex.	Aquitanien	-198.00
509.50	Série continentale lacustre et salifère du fossé bressan		Stampien calcaire. Calcaire argileux, niveaux de marne, présence de silex.	Stampien	-286.00

A.2. SUMMARY OF CIVIL ENGINEERING COST ESTIMATES

	Shafts (service and personnel)	Diameter	Depth	Cost per m	Direct cost (EUR)
PA	Services and personnel at point A	18	40	680,752.64	27,230,105
PB	Services and personnel at point B	12	45	381,666.13	17,174,976
PC	Services and personnel at point C	12	70	381,666.13	26,716,629
PD	Services and personnel at point D	12	60	381,666.13	22,899,968
PE	Services and personnel at point E	12	85	381,666.13	32,441,621
PF	Services and personnel at point F	12	65	381,666.13	24,808,298
PG	Services and personnel at point G	18	50	680,752.64	34,037,632
PH	Services and personnel at point H	12	60	381,666.13	22,899,968
PI	Services and personnel at point I	12	60	381,666.13	22,899,968
PJ	Services and personnel at point J	12	45	381,666.13	17,174,976
PK	Services and personnel at point K	12	55	381,666.13	20,991,637
PL	Services and personnel at point L	12	65	381,666.13	24,808,298
	Total		700		294,084,074

	Shafts (experiments)	Diameter	Depth	Cost per m	Direct cost (EUR)
PA	Experiment shaft at point A	15	40	514,446.24	20,577,850
PA	Second experimental shaft at point A	10	40	292,021.72	11,680,869
PB	Experiment shaft at point B	15	45	514,446.24	23,150,081
PB	Second experimental shaft at point B	10	45	292,021.72	13,140,978
PG	Experiment shaft at point G	15	50	514,446.24	25,722,312
PG	Second experimental shaft at point G	10	50	292,021.72	14,601,086
PL	Experiment shaft at point L	15	65	514,446.24	33,439,006
PL	Second experimental shaft at point L	10	65	292,021.72	18,981,412
	Total		400		161,293,594

	Construction Structures	Diameter	Depth	Cost per m	Direct cost (EUR)
	Construction Shaft near LHC P1	7	97	150,316	14,580,643
	Construction Accesses and ventilation shafts			Cost per m3	Direct cost (EUR)
T1	Construction shaft transfer line tunnel 1	7	420	1,276	82,485,192
T2	Construction shaft transfer line tunnel 2	7	530	1,276	104,088,456
T3	Construction shaft transfer line tunnel 3	7	140	1,276	27,495,064
T4	Construction shaft transfer line tunnel 4	7	160	1,276	31,422,930
	Total		1347		260,072,285

FUTURE CIRCULAR COLLIDER

10.5281/zenodo.4545604

Date: 01/12/2020

Description	Structure Length m	COSTS PER M (Direct Costs Only) EUR/m	Total Direct Costs EUR	Site Investigation (2%) EUR	Preliminary design, approvals and tender documents (10%) EUR	Project Changes/ Unforeseen Stoppages and Missed Items (2%) EUR	Contractor's Profit (3%) EUR	TOTAL COSTS EUR	COSTS PER M EUR/m
TOTAL PROJECT COSTS								7,304,050,011	
UNDERGROUND	182,278.00							6,636,475,974	36,409
Machine Tunnels	100,216	26,781	2,683,860,792	53,677,216	268,386,079	53,677,216	80,515,824	3,140,117,127	31,333
Transfer line	60,000	16,408	984,505,422	19,690,108	98,450,542	19,690,108	29,535,163	1,151,871,343	19,198
Injection caverns	80	129,149	10,331,945	206,639	1,033,194	206,639	309,958	12,088,376	151,105
Beam Dump caverns	100	75,477	7,547,650	150,953	754,765	150,953	226,430	8,830,751	88,308
Bypass Tunnels (TBM EPB)	5,250	26,781	140,598,998	2,811,980	14,059,900	2,811,980	4,217,970	164,500,827	31,333
Bypass Tunnels (conventional techniques)	3,129	22,898	71,647,966	1,432,959	7,164,797	1,432,959	2,149,439	83,828,120	26,791
Shafts (service and personnel)	700		294,084,074	5,881,681	29,408,407	5,881,681	8,822,522	344,078,367	491,541
Caverns (services)	1,190	328,930	391,427,284	7,828,546	39,142,728	7,828,546	11,742,819	457,969,922	384,849
Junction caverns	1,900	129,149	245,383,692	4,907,674	24,538,369	4,907,674	7,361,511	287,098,919	151,105
Electrical Alcoves	1,650	35,069	57,863,850	1,157,277	5,786,385	1,157,277	1,735,916	67,700,705	41,031
Experiments									
Shafts	400		161,293,594	3,225,872	16,129,359	3,225,872	4,838,808	188,713,505	471,784
Caverns	264	912,405	240,874,887	4,817,498	24,087,489	4,817,498	7,226,247	281,823,618	1,067,514
Connection Tunnels	1,230	9,271	11,403,799	228,076	1,140,380	228,076	342,114	13,342,444	10,848
Survey galleries	480	9,271	4,450,263	89,005	445,026	89,005	133,508	5,206,808	10,848
Klystron Gallery and Connections	572	20,544	11,751,386	235,028	1,175,139	235,028	352,542	13,749,122	24,037
Construction Accesses and ventilation shafts	1,347		260,072,285	5,201,446	26,007,228	5,201,446	7,802,169	304,284,573	225,898
Construction Access tunnels	3,770	25,226	95,103,802	1,902,076	9,510,380	1,902,076	2,853,114	111,271,448	29,515
SURFACE			558,062,624	11,161,252	55,806,262	11,161,252	16,741,879	652,933,270	
Experimental sites			229,217,210	4,584,344	22,921,721	4,584,344	6,876,516	268,184,136	
Access sites			328,845,414	6,576,908	32,884,541	6,576,908	9,865,362	384,749,135	
TEMPORARY WORKS			12,513,476	250,270	1,251,348	250,270	375,404	14,640,767	